

Package ‘goldeneye’

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Title Sharing Secrets Safely

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Description The goldeneye package is designed to allow data to safely be shared between R users over insecure channels. While it does require using R, the interfaces are written to be as simple as possible in order to reduce the technical barrier for beginner R users. A shiny interface is also provided to further simplify usage. This package was developed as part of the NordForsk-funded DigiVet project.

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goldeneye-package	<i>goldeneye: Sharing Secrets Safely</i>
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Description

The goldeneye package is designed to allow data to safely be shared between R users over insecure channels. While it does require using R, the interfaces are written to be as simple as possible in order to reduce the technical barrier for beginner R users. A shiny interface is also provided to further simplify usage. This package was developed as part of the NordForsk-funded DigiVet project.

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gf_saveRDS	<i>Save and read encrypted RDS</i>
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Description

Save and read encrypted RDS

Usage

```

gy_saveRDS(
  object,
  file = stop("file must be specified (.rdg file extension is recommended)"),
  users = character(0),
  local_user = TRUE,
  comment = "",
  overwrite = FALSE,
  ascii = FALSE,
  funs = list(type = "identity"),
  ...
)

gy_readRDS(
  file = stop("file must be specified (.rdg file extension is recommended)"),
  run_custom = TRUE
)

```

Arguments

object	the object to encrypt
file	the filename to which the encrypted object will be saved
users	one or more users who will be authorised to decrypt the file
local_user	should the local user be able to decrypt the file?
comment	a comment to include
overwrite	should the file be overwritten, if it exists?
ascii	argument passed to saveRDS
funs	argument passed to saveRDS
...	arguments passed to gy_serialise
run_custom	should any custom decryption functions be run automatically?

gy_encrypt

Encrypt and decrypt a pre-serialised object using goldeneye

Description

Encrypt and decrypt a pre-serialised object using goldeneye

Usage

```

gy_encrypt(
  object,
  users = character(0),
  local_user = TRUE,
  comment = "",
  funs = gy_key_funs("identity")
)

```

```
gy_decrypt(object, run_custom = TRUE)
```

```
get_public_keys(users, type = "curve")
```

Arguments

object	the serialised object to encrypt
users	a character vector of (other) users within your current user group for whom the encrypted file will be decryptable. Alternatively, this can be a vector of paths/urls to public keys, or a mixture of the two.
local_user	should the current user also be able to decrypt thw file?
comment	an optional comment that will be sent (unencrypted) along with the file
funs	optional additional encryption steps: this must be the output of a call to gy_key_funs
run_custom	should any custom decryption functions be run automatically?
type	the type of public key to return ("curve" or "ed")

gy_join_group	<i>Join an existing goldeneye user group via a weblink</i>
---------------	--

Description

Join an existing goldeneye user group via a weblink

Usage

```
gy_join_group(weblink = NULL, user = NULL, make_default = FALSE)
```

```
gy_set_group(group, make_default = FALSE, silent = FALSE)
```

Arguments

weblink	the weblink as provided by the group administrator
user	the username that you want to use for this group
make_default	should this become the default group?
group	the name of the group to set
silent	option to silence output

gy_key_funs	<i>Obtain key functions</i>
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Description

Obtain key functions

Usage

```
gy_key_funs(type)
```

Arguments

type	type of key function (only "identity" is currently supported)
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gy_profile	<i>Set a goldeneye profile and display user information</i>
------------	---

Description

Set a goldeneye profile and display user information

Usage

```
gy_profile(path = getOption("goldeneye_path"), silent = FALSE)
```

```
gy_info(silent = FALSE)
```

Arguments

path	path to goldeneye profile
silent	option to suppress output to screen

gy_public_file	<i>Extract the public key file</i>
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Description

Extract the public key file

Usage

```
gy_public_file(file = "goldeneye_public.gyu", silent = FALSE)
```

Arguments

file	filename to write to
silent	do this quietly?

gy_save	<i>Save and load encrypted files</i>
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Description

Save and load encrypted files

Usage

```

gy_save(
  ...,
  list = character(),
  file = stop("file must be specified (.rdg file extension is recommended)"),
  users = character(),
  local_user = TRUE,
  comment = "",
  overwrite = FALSE,
  funs = list(type = "identity"),
  method = "qs"
)

gy_load(
  file = stop("file must be specified (.rdg file extension is recommended)")
)

```

Arguments

...	one or more R objects to encrypt
list	alternative method to provide R objects to encrypt as a character vector
file	the name of the encrypted file to create/load (a .rdg file extension is recommended)
users	a character vector of (other) users within your current user group for whom the encrypted file will be decryptable. Alternatively, this can be a vector of paths/urls to public keys, or a mixture of the two.
local_user	should the current user also be able to decrypt thw file?
comment	an optional comment that will be sent (unencrypted) along with the
overwrite	if a file with the same name already exists, should it be overwritten?
funs	optional additional encryption steps: this must be the output of a call to gy_key_funs
method	the serialisation method to use (currently either 'qs' or 'base')

gy_serialise

Serialise and deserialise a list of objects/files

Description

Serialise and deserialise a list of objects/files

Usage

```

gy_serialise(object, files = character(), method = "qs", ...)

gy_deserialise(object, files = TRUE, ...)

gy_serialize(object, files = character(), method = "qs", ...)

gy_deserialize(object, files = TRUE, ...)

```

Arguments

object	the object to encrypt
files	external files to serialise (not yet implemented)
method	the serialisation method to use (base, qs, or custom)
...	arguments passed to the underlying serialisation method

gy_setup	<i>Setup a new goldeyene encryption profile</i>
----------	---

Description

Setup a new goldeyene encryption profile

Usage

```
gy_setup(
  name = NULL,
  email = NULL,
  filename = NULL,
  path = NULL,
  append_Rprofile = NULL,
  silent = FALSE
)
```

Arguments

name	your full name
email	your email address
filename	the filename to which the profile will be saved
path	the path in which to save the profile
append_Rprofile	should the R profile file be appended to automatically load this profile when R is restarted?
silent	option to suppress output

gy_users	<i>Obtain a list of users for a given group</i>
----------	---

Description

Obtain a list of users for a given group

Usage

```
gy_users(group = NULL, refresh = FALSE)
```

Arguments

group	the group for which to return users (defaults to the active group)
refresh	should the list be refreshed from the remote/online location?

Description

Zip and encrypt external files using goldeneye

Usage

```
gy_zip(
  input_files,
  file = stop("file must be specified (.rfg file extension is recommended)"),
  compression_level = 5,
  users = character(0),
  local_user = TRUE,
  comment = "",
  funs = gy_key_funs("identity")
)

gy_unzip(
  file = stop("file must be specified (.rfg file extension is recommended)"),
  directory = getwd(),
  unzip = TRUE,
  overwrite = FALSE,
  run_custom = TRUE
)
```

Arguments

<code>input_files</code>	one or more files to add to the zip archive
<code>file</code>	the filename to which the encrypted object will be saved
<code>compression_level</code>	compression level to use on a scale of 1-9 (passed to zip)
<code>users</code>	a character vector of (other) users within your current user group for whom the encrypted file will be decryptable. Alternatively, this can be a vector of paths/urls to public keys, or a mixture of the two.
<code>local_user</code>	should the current user also be able to decrypt thw file?
<code>comment</code>	an optional comment that will be sent (unencrypted) along with the file
<code>funs</code>	optional additional encryption steps: this must be the output of a call to gy_key_funs
<code>directory</code>	the directory to which the decrypted/unzipped files will be saved
<code>unzip</code>	should the decrypted files also be unzipped?
<code>overwrite</code>	should the file be overwritten, if it exists?
<code>run_custom</code>	should any custom decryption functions be run automatically?

run_app

Launch shiny application

Description

Launch shiny application

Usage

run_app()

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